

SPATIAL INEQUITY AND DEVELOPMENT IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA : A
GEOGRAPHIC INFORMATION SYSTEM (GIS) PERSPECTIVE.

Joseph C. Udoh and Akan A. Tom

Department of Geography and Regional Planning, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Uyo
Uyo, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

It is the responsibility of the various levels of government in any nation to conceive, initiate, plan and implement numerous development projects and programs spanning across all sectors of the economy. Overcoming inequalities in the distribution of these development efforts constitutes one of the major problems facing planners in different parts of the world. There is the need to analyze the degree the distribution of services is equitably distributed within a territory. When such an investigation stresses the question of need, fairness or justice, spatial equity is involve. This paper utilizes geographic Information system (GIS) techniques to analyze spatial inequity and in the process create an objective criterion that could help policy makers bridge the gap in development in the study area. By identifying and mapping development components (infrastructural development and population quality) the study identified current development trends and singles out seven Local Government Areas (LGA) that need remedial actions so as to reduce the level of developmental imbalance in Akwa Ibom State of Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

It is the responsibility of the various levels of government in any nation to conceive, initiate, plan and implement numerous development projects and programs spanning across all sectors of the economy. Overcoming inequalities in the distribution of these development efforts constitutes one of the major problems facing planners in different parts of the world. In Nigeria, inequalities in the level of socio-economic development in the component units seem to be an obvious phenomenon. Abumere (1998) used the term “distributional inequity” to explain differences in availability of the gains of economic development among the populations in the nation’s areal units. There is the need to analyze the degree the distribution of services is equitably distributed within a territory. When such an investigation stresses the question of need, fairness or justice, spatial equity is involved (Talen and Selin, 1998).

According to Abumere (1998), judging by the disparity in development between the various constituent units, Nigeria comprises of two nations – the have and the have-nots. The recognition of this fact can either motivate backward communities to embark on development projects to catch up with their developed neighbors, or can lead to grudge, discontent and sometimes strife where the neighbor’s advantage is believed to be unjustly acquired. The backwardness of some areas may even cause a serious slow down on the wheel of progress of the entire nation (Akpan, 2000). Hence, the need to monitor the distribution of development efforts within and between the different components of the Nation is paramount so that harmony and spatial equality could be attained.

Haggins (2009) explored the regional inequality in Nigeria focusing especially in the Niger Delta. It examines the government of Nigeria’s response to the marginalization of the Niger Delta and concludes that development of the delta since the establishment of Niger Delta Development Authority (NDDC) -a body set up to address the neglected area - has been slow. It concluded that the natural resource endowments of the region have not been translated to welfare gains to the communities.

Peters *et al* (1994) asserts that successful economic development is a process that fills the different needs for the different communities at different times in any region. Also, the level of economic development of

any state is a factor of the quality of its population and educational system. Hence, in the planning of development projects, a wide variety of data is needed so as to satisfy the different shades of stakeholders. Generally the inability to recognize the importance of information on development militates against Nigeria's efforts in nation building. Adeniyi (1993), Uluocha (2003), and, Ukpong and Udoh (2005) have all emphasized the need for the acquisition of spatial data about the people, resources and the environment as a precondition for transformational development. In this regard, the attempt to categorize the Nigerian space according to the levels of development is often hindered by the problem of measurement and data (Abumere, 1998).

The World Bank (2011) puts the population of Nigeria at 154 million making it the largest country in Africa and accounting for about 47% of the population of West Africa. With about 200 ethnic groups and 500 indigenous languages, the country is fragmented along geographical, ethnic and cultural identity. Positive economic progress recorded for Nigeria in recent years include the 8.9% increase in non-oil growth in 2006; successful negotiation and clearing of foreign debt; and, the successful transition to democracy following the 4th consecutive democratic elections, the latest being in April 2011. These developments have strengthened Nigeria's profile in the international profile. Despite the fact that Nigeria is the world's 13th largest oil producer, 6th largest in Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC), the rise in oil wealth has not translated into a significant increase in the standard of living. Increases in oil revenue have however coincided with a rise in poverty and inequality in the country (Higgins, 2009)

The aim of this study is to assess the level of distributional inequity in Akwa Ibom State of Nigeria using the Geographic Information System (GIS) – a technology - based strategy that arms policy makers with objective tools for equitable decision making . By identifying the development components; creating of a computer database; producing and analyzing a development zone maps of the study area; the study analyses the current development of the study areas, and in the process identifies areas of need for remedial actions.

Different methods other than the GIS have been used by researchers to monitor spatial inequalities and inequity in different parts of the world. For an Example, Akpan (1995) used 24 LGAs in Akwa Ibom State as the observation unit to collect data on 26 socio economic variables upon which factor analysis was performed to obtain 7 major dimensions of inequality. Also, Chazireni (2003) used the composite index method to rank and demarcate administrative districts of Zimbabwe according to the level of development. Abumere (1998) used 19 variables to assess the distributional inequity in Nigeria and concluded that the access gap between the north and south is widening.

GIS as a fast developing technology is designed to collect, store, manipulate data where geographical location is important to the analysis (Aronoff, 1995). As a decision support system, it is attracting policy planners as it helps integrate a wide variety of datasets and presents the results in a visually stimulating manner. Development is hypothesized in this paper as a combination of infrastructural development and Human Development Index based indicators that measure the quality of the population. This approach allowed different categories of data on development components to be collected and analyzed in a computer environment.

THE STUDY AREA

Created on September 23rd, 1987 out of Cross River State (Fig.1); Akwa Ibom State (Fig.1) is situated between latitudes 4⁰⁰1'N and 5⁰⁴5'N and longitudes 7⁰²5'E and 8⁰²5'E. The state is bounded on the North by Abia State, the South by the Bight of Bonny, on the East by Cross River State and on the West by Rivers State (Figure 1). It covers a total land area of 8, 412.2 square kilometer (NPC 2002). With the total population of the 31 Local Government Areas being 3.9 million people (FGN, 2009), the state has an average population density of 466.02 persons per km².

The landscape of Akwa Ibom State is generally low-lying with no portion exceeding 175 meters above sea level. The whole state is traversed and criss-crossed by a large number of rivers, rivulets, streams and creeks. The climate of the state is characterized by two seasons – rainy or wet season. However, there is no month of the year that Akwa Ibom State does not receive rainfall on the average. The only difference is in the quantity of the rainfall received. While the rainy season lasts from late March to October, the dry season is from November to March. The total annual rainfall is high hence emphasizing the effect of South West winds all the year round. The total annual average rainfall is about 2500mm (Ekanem, 2010). Temperatures are uniformly high throughout the year with slight variation between 26^o and 28^o (AKS, 1989). The climate of the state favors luxuriant tropical rainforest. The native vegetation has been almost completely replaced by secondary forest of predominantly wild oil shrubs and grass undergrowth.

Akwa Ibom state is located in the Niger Delta of Nigeria which contributes the bulk of the foreign exchange earnings of the country. Oil from the delta completely dominates the economy of Nigeria. From 1970 to 1999, oil generated about \$231 billion for the country’s economy. Oil accounted for about 79.5% of total government revenues and around 97% of foreign exchange revenue between 2000 and 2004 (UNDP, 2006; Higgins, 2009). As noted earlier, the contributions of the region to the Nigerian economy has not brought commensurate gains to the Niger delta. Instead environmental degradation, neglect and poverty have attracted worldwide attention. Over the years, intervention strategies have been introduced to address the development challenges of the region. One of such efforts is the Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC) established in 1992. The Federal Government of Nigeria has shown renewing commitments towards the development of the region.

Akwa Ibom as one of the states in the Niger Delta has benefited from the activities of the NDDC. The state has been chosen for the study as it reflects the development needs of the region. The state has also benefitted in recent years from increased funding as one of the oil producing states. The need therefore arises for an equitable distribution strategy of development efforts throughout the 31 LGAs of the state.

Fig.1.1: Akwa Ibom State (The Study Area)

METHODOLOGY

Data input, weights and conversion.

Two sets of data were used for this work. In the first set, data on infrastructural (facility) development were collated from relevant government agencies and existing records. The second set of data were those of the Human Development Index based Quality of the Population.

Infrastructural Development Indicators: Data on health, education, transport, industrial, and communication facilities, derived from AK-SEEDS (2004), for each of the 31 LGAs of the state, were used as indicators of facility development. As shown on Table 1, the indicators of each component facility were then allocated weights based on their perceived contribution to the individual component. Hence, Teaching hospital was weighted 10 in the health component because of its relative importance to the health sector of the state. Others were accordingly weighted and summarized in Table 2.

Table 1: Allocated Weights Of Development Components/Indicators

	Components	Indicators	Weight
1	Health	Teaching Hospital	10
		General Hospitals	5
		Health Centers	4
		Primary Health Centers	3
		Others	2
2	Education	Tertiary Schools	5
		Technical Colleges	4
		Secondary Schools	3
		Primary Schools	2
3	Transportation	Federal and State Roads (Tarred)	5
		Federal Road (Earth)	4
		State Road (Earth)/L. Govt. Road (Tarred)	3
		L .Govt. Road (Earth)	2
4	Industrial	Federal Govt. Industries	5
		State Govt. Industries	4
5	Communication	Media(TV, Radio, Newspaper)	5
		Post Office	4
		Telephone Access	3
		Sub post Office	2
		Postal Agencies	2

Source: Analysis by the authors

Population Quality Data:

Five data quality parameters were used for the study: Human Development Index (HDI), Gross Domestic Product (GDP) Index, and Life Expectancy Index were obtained from UNDP Human Development Survey (UNDP 2006) while data on Poverty Index was obtained from Ekpo and Uwatt (2004).

Data Manipulation

The political map of the state obtained from Ministry of Lands and Town Planning on a scale of 1:125,000 were scanned into a GIS environment, geo- referenced, and digitized. The attribute table of each LGA, digitized as a polygon was used to link the Facility and Population Quality data to create the base maps used for the GIS analysis. The base maps were converted from vector based shape files to grids (raster based). The conversion made it possible to use all data sets that were connected to shape file with administrative boundaries for further analysis and modeling.

Table 2: Development Indicators of Akwa Ibom State

LGA		PROJECT DEVELOPMENT*					POP. QUALITY			
		EDUC.	HEAL TH.	TRANS.	IND.	COMM.	HDI**	POV_INDEX*	GDP_INDEX**	LIFE_EXP**
1.	ABAK	126	47	1706	5	22	0.315	83.64	0.121	0.4920
2.	EASTERN OBOLO	29	15	45	0	2	0.261	50.82	0.000	0.4580
3.	EKET	82	36	1074	12	11	0.440	78.31	0.581	0.4170
4.	ESIT EKET	46	28	50	0	6	0.346	49.74	0.253	0.4750
5.	ESSIEN UDIM	135	61	1565	0	0	0.312	66.67	0.112	0.5000
6.	ETIM EKPO	102	47	614	0	16	0.280	59.56	0.070	0.4920
7.	ETINAN	115	71	765	5	27	0.355	30.81	0.005	0.5170
8.	IBENO	54	20	462	6	7	0.355	53.37	0.253	0.5000
9.	IBESIKPO ASUTAN	121	34	1047	0	13	0.365	75.13	0.281	0.4830
10.	IBIONO IBOM	146	60	0	0	2	0.372	26.88	0.309	0.4830
11.	IKA	45	26	410	0	15	0.481	45.93	0.714	0.4250
12.	IKONO	154	44	0	0	6	0.260	43.98	0.072	0.4330
13.	IKOT ABASI	80	32	988	8	18	0.505	45.33	0.745	0.4830
14.	IKOT EKPENE	94	50	2600	14	65	0.449	36.59	0.563	0.4830
15.	INI	112	40	0	0	0	0.370	41.21	0.226	0.5330
16.	ITU	98	26	1500	20	37	0.294	39.79	0.000	0.5250
17.	MBO	63	31	696	0	6	0.320	56.18	0.258	0.4080
18.	MKPAT ENIN	141	46	1016	0	14	0.276	45.60	0.167	0.3920
19.	NSIT ATAI	64	21	543	0	10	0.369	77.04	0.354	0.4420
20.	NSIT IBOM	112	47	424	0	27	0.471	69.35	0.571	0.5170
21.	NSIT UBIUM	112	38	832	0	21	0.339	45.23	0.174	0.5330

Table 2 Cont.....

22.	OBOT AKARA	85	20	0	0	6	0.262	59.38	0.000	0.4750
23.	OKOBO	82	28	474	0	15	0.354	46.48	0.295	0.4670
24.	ONNA	79	46	485	0	16	0.254	45.70	0.063	0.4170
25.	ORON	44	24	946	6	3	0.309	66.67	0.233	0.5330
26.	ORUK ANAM	144	62	1664	0	20	0.257	30.96	0.063	0.4250
27.	UDUNG UKO	23	31	0	0	7	0.294	90.36	0.043	0.5080
28.	UKANAFUN	139	25	1485	0	12	0.337	67.20	0.258	0.4750
29.	URUAN	117	30	1958	0	13	0.313	71.36	0.139	0.4830
30.	URUE OFFONG ORUKO	54	25	333	0	5	0.256	77.89	0.000	0.4750
31.	UYO	182	37	723	35	29	0.339	68.75	0.284	0.5750

Sources: *Project Development data (derived from AK-SEEDS (2004); **HDI,GDP_Index, & Life Expectancy (UNDP, 2006); Poverty Index (Uwatt and Ekpo,2005).

Table 4: Areal Coverage of Infrastructural Development

Infrastructural Dev. Zones	Area (km ²)	%
1. Low	1158.01	17.16
2. Medium	5291.54	78.39
3. High	301	4.46

Source: Analysis by the authors

Population Quality Surface:

As was the case with Facility Development, the components of the Population Quality were each classified into Low, Medium and High quality zones using the classification scheme shown in Table 5.

The resultant map produced by the combination of the five components is presented in Fig.3.

Table 5: Population Quality Component– Classification scheme

Zones	Population Quality Components				
	Poverty Incident (%)	HDI	Life Expectancy	Education Index	GDP- Index
1. Low	26 – 48.08	0.254 – 0.336	0.392 – 0.453	0.270 – 0.299	0 – 0.248
2. Medium	48.05 – 69.20	0.337 – 0.421	0.454 – 0.514	0.300 – 0.328	0.249 – 0.496
3. High	69.21 – 90.36	0.422-0.504	0.515 – 0.575	0.329 – 0.357	0.497 – 0.746

Source: Analysis by the authors

Fig 3: Pop. Quality Zones

Table 6: Areal coverage of Population Quality component

Pop Quality Zone	Area (km ²)	%
1. Low	1369.71	20.03
2. Medium	1979.64	28.96
3. High	3487.23	51.01

Source: Analysis by the authors

Table 6 and Figure 3 show that 13 LGAs constitute 51.01% of the high population quality zone with most of them found in the northern and south western part of the state. 28.96% and 20.03% of the state are in the medium and low population quality zones respectively. While 10 LGAs are in the medium, 8 are in the low zones.

Fig.3: Akwa Ibom State - Population Quality

The Final Development Surface

A combination of the facility development and population quality surfaces using the Single Output tool of Arcmap 9.1 software with a 50% weight for each component produced the final development surface shown in Figure 4. It shows that 7 LGAs are in the high development zone, 10 in medium and 14 in the low development zones. table 7 shows that 37.29% of the area is found in the low zone, 34.61% in medium and 28.11% in the low development zone.

Fig.3: Population Quality Zones

Table 7: Areal coverage of the Final development surface.

Dev. Zones	Area (km2)	%
1. Low	2551.37	37.29
2. Medium	2368.08	34.61
3. High	1923.27	28.11

Source: Analysis by the authors

THE RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

Using facility development and population quality indicators the paper has used GIS techniques to demarcate and map Akwa Ibom State into three LGA based development zones – high, medium and low. The final development surface produced has shown that while 7 LGAs are found in the High zone, 10 in medium and 14 in low development zones.

The results show that Uyo (hosting the state capital), Ikot Ekpene, Itu, Essien Udim, Mkpato Enin, Oruk Anam and Ukanafun LGAs are in the high development zone. These LGAs can be said to be those favored by the combination of infrastructural development combined with a high human development indicators. Although one may not argue with the inclusion Uyo and Ikot Ekpene in this group, the inclusion of Oruk Anam is highly debatable as it is located far away from the state capital. A common characteristic of the LGA in the low development zone is that most of them are all located far away from the capital Uyo. Ini, Etim Ekpo, Ika and Obot Akara are all located in the North and North Western border of the State with Abia state. They can therefore be said to be neglected as they are far away from the Uyo capital city which can be seen as the center of development. The rest of the LGAs in the low development zone are all coastal LGAs bordering the Atlantic Ocean.

GIS has often been described as a decision support tool that enables policy makers make objective decisions devoid of subjective considerations that could lead to an equitable distribution of development efforts. The study has revealed, using GIS techniques an objective technique that would help policy makers understand the pattern of distribution of development efforts. By linking facilities on ground with the characteristics of the population; the bases for choosing areas for the distribution of facilities have been provided.

The findings of this work agree with previous researches (Haggins, 2009; Abumere, 2000; Akpan, 1995) concerning the imbalance in the distribution of facilities within the various components of the Nigerian state. Despite various intervention agencies like the NDDC, the bridging of development gap has been very slow despite the natural resource endowment of the units concerned (Haggins, 2009).

CONCLUSION

The study has demonstrated the capabilities of GIS in analyzing inequalities in development efforts in Akwa Ibom state. GIS provided an objective way of showing the differences in development and has helped in devising strategies for addressing the imbalance. GIS provides informed decision support alternatives, approaches and possibilities to development planners. This approach will help eliminate some of the current inequitable development practices that are not only subjective but conflict generating.

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Corresponding author

Joseph C. Udoh

Department of Geography and Regional Planning, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Uyo, Uyo, Nigeria

email: joseph_udoh@yahoo.com